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Fatty Acid Profile And Storage Stability Of Bread From Mushroom Supplemented Composite Of Wheat/Plantain And Cinnamon Powder.

Ifeoluwa Iremide David-Oluwole

Department of Food Sciences and Technology, School of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology, Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria
Ifedavid25@gmail.com

Bai-Bureh O'Bai Kamara

Sierra Leone Agricultural Research Institute (SLARI)
[Department of Agriculture, Faculty of Basic Sciences, Central University, Mile 91, Sierra Leone.](mailto:kamarabaiburobai@gmail.com)
kamarabaiburobai@gmail.com

Raji Deborah Ayomide

Department of Food Sciences and Technology, School of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology, Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria
deborah1raji@gmail.com

Babalola Karimot

Department of Food Sciences and Technology, School of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology, Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria
emiolakarimot424@gmail.com

Ahmid Chernor Jalloh

Youth Action for Relentless Development Organization- Sierra Leone (YARDO-SL)
ahmidjalloh99@gmail.com

Ojuri Ademola Gabriel

Department of Food Sciences and Technology, School of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology, Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria
ademolaojuri@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The study assessed the fatty acid profile and storage stability of bread from composite blend of wheat, plantain, *Pleurotus ostreatus* (oyster mushroom), and cinnamon powder in varying ratios. The functional properties of the composite flour were also determined. The plantain and mushroom were processed, milled, and blended with commercial all-purpose flour to create four unique formulations alongside a control sample. The flour blends were created, combining all-purpose flour, plantain flour, mushroom, and cinnamon powder in ratios 100:0:0:0 (Z5A), 70:30:0:0 (Y2B), 70:25:5:0 (C3X), 65:20:10:5 (W2D), and 65:15:15:5 (V1E). Significant ($p < 0.05$) differences were observed in the flour blends' functional properties except for bulk density. Fatty acid analysis revealed linoleic acid (18:2) as the most abundant, with concentrations ranging from 35.74 mg/g to 49.81 mg/g. The moisture content of the bread samples throughout storage ranged between 28.8% and 38.4%. The peroxide values increased with the inclusion of cinnamon and mushroom into the bread; however, C3X was able to maintain a stable value during storage. The findings suggest that bread with a plantain-mushroom-cinnamon flour ratio of 20%-10%-5% (W2D), respectively, presents a viable, nutritionally enhanced alternative to conventional bread.

Keywords: Functional properties, flour blend, fatty acid profile, storage stability, Oyster mushroom.

1. Introduction

Over time, people have started demanding more nutritious and functional food and this can be attributed to the increasing awareness of the importance of a healthy diet in human health and well-being. To increase the nutritional value of food, such as bread can be increased using unconventional ingredients such as vegetables, fruits and even insects, showing the need for further investigation on the nutritional quality and sensory assessment of these novel food products.

Plantain (*Musa paradisiaca*) is a staple food in Central and West Africa. Nigeria produces about 2.11 million metric tonnes annually, with about 35%-60% post-harvest losses (FAO, 2004). Oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) is a popular edible mushroom with high nutritional value. *Pleurotus ostreatus* is an edible mushroom and is among the easiest mushrooms to cultivate. It has been extensively investigated for its nutritional qualities, including its protein, fibre, vitamins, and mineral content (Sánchez, 2004). Cinnamon has been used in traditional medicine due to its antimicrobial, antifungal, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties, etc. (Shahrajabian & Sun, 2023). This study evaluates the fatty acid composition, functional properties and storage stability of bread supplemented with oyster mushroom, unripe plantain and cinnamon powder.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sources of materials and preparation

Oyster Mushroom spawn (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) was obtained from the Federal Institute for Industrial Research (FIRO), Oshodi and cultivated in the FUTA environment. Ethanol, calcium carbonate and calcium sulphite from Pascal Scientific Laboratory, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria. Other materials used in the cultivation of the mushroom, such as polyethene bags, rice bran, cotton wool etc. and Unripe Plantain and cinnamon powder were purchased from the main market in Akure, Ondo State. The desiccators, petri dishes, and drying ovens used were those of the Department of Food Science and Technology, Federal University of Technology, Akure.

Oyster Mushroom cultivation and production.

The cultivation and production of fresh oyster mushrooms and powder were done as described by

Bello *et al.*, (2017) with slight modifications

Formulation table

SAMPLE	ALL PURPOSE FLOUR (%)	UNRIPE		
		PLANTAIN FLOUR (%)	MUSHROOM POWDER (%)	CINNAMON (%)
Z5A	100	-	-	-
Y2B	70	30	-	-
C3X	70	25	5	-
W2D	65	20	10	5
V1E	65	15	15	5

The bread samples were produced using the flour blends as described in Table 1

Bread Production

This method involves the addition of all ingredients; composite flour (800 g), sugar (48 g), salt (16 g), milk (25 g), yeast (using 0.5 Mc Farland standard), fat (48 g) and water (250 ml) at mixing stage and kneading to obtain the dough. The bread was produced using the method described by Cauvian (2015).

Functional Properties of the Mushroom supplemented composite Wheat /Plantain Flour

The bulk density and swelling capacity was determined according to the method described by Okaka and Potter (1977). The water and oil absorption capacities were determined by the method of Sosulski *et al.*, (1976). The least gelation concentration was determined using the method of Coffman and Garcia (1977). The Narayana and Narasinga Rao (1982) with slight modifications was used for determining Foaming capacity (FC).

Storage stability studies of the mushroom supplemented Bread

The bread samples were packed in Polypropylene (PP) and stored in an incubator at ambient temperature (28 ± 2 °C). were evaluated for moisture content, free fatty acid (FFA), thiobarbituric acid (TBA), and peroxide value at 3 days intervals for a period of 14 days.

The moisture content was determined by using oven-drying (AOAC, 1990). The FFA value was determined using the method of Pearson (1970). The TBA value was determined using the method of Pearson (1970). The peroxide value, expressed in milliequivalents of peroxide per kilogram of fat (meq/kg), was calculated from the titration data and recorded for each storage interval (AOAC, 2016).

Fatty acid Profile of the mushroom supplemented Bread.

The fatty acid profile was determined using gas chromatography (GC). First, the lipid extraction was carried out by weighing 5 g of the sample and using a solvent mixture of chloroform and methanol (2:1 v/v). The extracted lipids were then converted into fatty acid methyl esters (FAME) by transesterification with methanolic potassium hydroxide (KOH). The FAMES were injected into a gas chromatograph equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID) and a capillary column. The oven temperature was programmed to start at 140°C, then increase to 240°C at a rate of 4°C/min. The carrier gas (nitrogen) was used at a constant flow rate. The detector and injector temperatures were maintained at 250°C. The fatty acids were identified by comparing their retention times with those of known FAME standards, and their concentrations were quantified based on the peak areas in the chromatogram (AOAC, 2016)

Statistical Analysis

The experimental results were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) of three replicates. Data obtained were statistically analyzed using one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), a tool in

Statistical Packages for Social Scientists (SPSS 18.0). The level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Means were separated with Duncan's New Multiple Range Test (DNMRT).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Functional Properties of the Composite Mushroom/Plantain Flour

Each functional property plays an important role in determining the flour's performance in food products and its interaction with other ingredients during processing. Table 2 shows the functional properties of all purpose – plantain-mushroom-cinnamon composite flours. The WAC and OAC ranged from 2.2 to 3.0 ml and 1.8 to 3.1 ml respectively. V1E has the highest WAC at 3.0 ml, largely due to its higher proportion of mushroom flour, which is rich in protein and fiber, both contributing to enhanced water absorption. The bulk density ranged from 0.61 to 0.65 g/ml with no significant difference ($p < 0.005$) between samples which is influenced by the structure of starch polymers and loose structure of the starch polymer which could result in low bulk density. The flour blend had a foam capacity ranging from 14.05 to 17.95 ml with YB4 having the highest foam capacity, which may be due to plantain flour's high starch content, contributing to increased foam formation (Adejuyitan *et al.*, 2009). Least Gelation Capacity (LGC) ranged from 0.7% to 1.8 %. The results indicate the addition of oyster mushroom and cinnamon powder enhances the gelling ability due to the protein and polysaccharides in mushrooms which promote gel formations. Swelling Capacity (SC) ranged from 0.5 to 1.3 ml with C3X (1.3ml) having the highest swelling capacity likely due to the higher fiber content in plantain and mushroom flours, which can absorb more water. Emulsion Capacity in this study ranged from 2.15 to 2.50 %.

Table 2: Functional properties of bread samples

Sample	WAC (ml)	OAC (ml)	B/D (g/ml)	FC (ml)	LGC (%)	SC (ml)	EC (%)
Z5A	2.4 ^b ± 0	2.0 ^{cc} ± 0	0.61 ^a ± 0	14.9 ^c ± 0.14	1.6 ^d ± 0	0.5 ^a ± 0	2.15 ^a ± 0.07
YB4	2.6 ^c ± 0	1.8 ^a ± 0	0.62 ^a ± 0	17.95 ^d ± 0.07	1.8 ^e ± 0	1.1 ^c ± 0	2.20 ^a ± 0
C3X	2.2 ^a ± 0	3.1 ± 0 ^d	0.65 ^a ± 0	13.15 ^a ± 0.07	0.9 ^c ± 0	1.3 ^d ± 0	2.5 ^c ± 0.14
W2D	2.6 ^c ± 0	2.1 ± 0 ^c	0.65 ^a ± 0	15.05 ^c ± 0.07	0.7 ^a ± 0	0.6 ^b ± 0	2.25 ^{ab} ± 0.07
V1E	3.0 ^d ± 0	1.8 ^a ± 0	0.61 ^a ± 0	14.05 ^b ± 0.07	0.8 ^b ± 0	0.6 ^b ± 0	2.45 ^{bc} ± 0.07

Values are means of triplicate determination (±SD). Mean values in the same column with the same superscript of alphabet are not significantly different at $P \leq 0.05$.

Z5A: 100% all-purpose flour (control); YB4: 70% all-purpose flour + 30% plantain flour; C3X: 70% all-purpose flour + 25% plantain flour + 5% Mushroom powder; W2D: 65% all-purpose flour + 20% plantain flour + 10% Mushroom powder + 5% Cinnamon powder; V1E: 65% all-purpose flour + 15% plantain flour + 15% Mushroom powder + 5% Cinnamon powder

Storage Stability

The moisture content of the bread samples throughout the duration of storage ranged between 38.4 and 34.6%, 36.0 and 34.7%, 33.3 and 28.8%, 33.0 and 33.1%, 37.4-37.3% for control (Z5A-100%), 70:30:0:0 (YB4), 70:25:5 (C3X), 65:20:10:5 (W2D), 65:15:15:5 (V1E) respectively. It was observed as significant decrease in the moisture content of Z5A and C3X which usually happens during storage as the crumb becomes drier. A significant release of FFA in the bread samples was observed during storage (Fig. 1). The pH decreased with storage time, it ranged between 6.2 and 3.8, 6.1 and 3.5, 6.1 and 2.8, 6.2 and 3.3, 6.2 and 4.4 % for control (Z5A) YB4, C3X, W2D, V1E respectively. V1E had the highest value indicating an increased decomposition of the bread sample. In comparison to the control (Z5A), samples YB4 and C3X (70:30:0:0 and 70:25:5 respectively)

were able to maintain low peroxide value showing a slower rate of spoilage. Thiobarbituric Acid value measures the level of oxidative rancidity in fats. The TBA values increased significantly for all bread samples over the 13-day storage period. V1E showed the highest increase from 0.57 to 15.77 over 13 days of storage at room temperature.

Figure 1: Chemical properties of bread stored at room temperature for 13 day.

Fatty Acid Profile

Fatty acid composition is crucial for evaluating the nutritional and functional qualities of food products, particularly for cardiovascular health and overall lipid metabolism. The fatty acids in food, especially polyunsaturated and monounsaturated fats, contribute to reducing the risk of chronic diseases (Simopoulos, 2008). Table 3 below highlights the different fatty acid profiles of five bread samples. Linoleic Acid (18:2) is a polyunsaturated fatty acid and was dominant fatty acid in the bread sample ranging from 35.74 to 49.81 mg/g, the high level of linoleic acid in samples C3X, W2D and V1E may be due to the inclusion mushroom and cinnamon powder which are both rich in polyunsaturated fatty acids (Manzi *et al.*, 2001). Linoleic acid is a polyunsaturated omega-6 fatty acid that plays a key role in maintaining cell membrane integrity and overall cardiovascular health (Simopoulos, 2008).

Table 3: Fatty Acid Profile of bread samples (mg/g)

Sample	Palmitic Acid	Palmitoleic Acid	Stearic Acid	Oleic Acid	Linoleic Acid (18:2)	Linoleic Acid (18:3)
Z5A	3.34	0.91	1.55	3.25	38.07	1.83
YB4	2.36	0.74	1.41	1.57	35.74	0.98
C3X	4.73	0.96	1.81	4.17	41.51	2.31
W2D	6.25	2.40	3.27	6.11	49.81	3.64
V1E	5.21	2.23	2.29	5.41	47.23	3.53

Z5A: 100% all-purpose flour (control); YB4: 70% all-purpose flour + 30% plantain flour; C3X: 70% all-purpose flour + 25% plantain flour + 5% Mushroom powder; W2D: 65% all-purpose flour + 20% plantain flour + 10% Mushroom powder + 5% Cinnamon powder;

CONCLUSION

Bread samples containing mushroom and cinnamon were found to contain a significant amount of fatty acid in comparison to bread with just all-purpose flour and plantain flour. The addition of plantain, oyster mushroom, and cinnamon flour to the flour blend showed no significant change in the bulk density among the other functional properties indicating the blends can be easily packaged. The fortification of bread with plantain, oyster mushroom and cinnamon flour increased the nutritional content and had various effects on the chemical properties during storage. Sample V1E was found to have the highest rate of staling among bread samples.

The W2D formulation represents a significant advancement in the development of functional, fortified bread products. Its superior fatty acid content and reduced staling rate demonstrate the potential of integrating locally available, nutrient-dense ingredients into staple foods. This research not only provides a viable solution for the fortification of bread for health-conscious individuals but also contributes to broader goals of sustainable food systems, nutritional security, and agricultural value addition in resource-limited contexts. Further research is warranted to optimize processing parameters, assess consumer acceptability, and evaluate the scalability of this formulation for commercial production.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the analyses of the various bread samples, the sample containing 65% all-purpose flour, 20% plantain flour, 15% oyster mushroom powder and 5% cinnamon powder (W2D) has the highest amount fatty acids and slowest stalling rate, this composition ratio can be adapted to the fortification of bread for health-conscious individuals.

The W2D formulation exemplifies how biological solutions can transform staple food production. By valorizing plantain, oyster mushrooms, and cinnamon crops that are well-suited

to tropical agroecological conditions this innovation supports agricultural diversification, creates new income streams for smallholder farmers, and reduces post-harvest losses. Furthermore, the extended shelf-life addresses food waste challenges, while the enhanced nutritional profile contributes to improved dietary diversity and public health outcomes. The W2D formulation exhibited the highest total fatty acid content among all samples analyzed. This finding is particularly significant given the growing consumer awareness regarding the health benefits of dietary lipids. Oyster mushrooms (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) are recognized as a rich source of polyunsaturated fatty acids, including linoleic acid, which is an essential omega-6 fatty acid linked to cardiovascular health and anti-inflammatory properties. Similarly, plantain flour contributes medium-chain fatty acids that are more readily metabolized for energy compared to long-chain fatty acids. The synergistic combination of these ingredients, further enhanced by the bioactive compounds in cinnamon, results in a bread product with an improved lipid profile compared to conventional wheat bread. This makes W2D an attractive option for health-conscious individuals seeking functional foods that support metabolic health.

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